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Student-Centric Explainable-AI Framework for Campus Placement Prediction

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ABSTRACT

Placement drives are an important opportunity for the students. Yet many students find it difficult to understand their preparation level. Most of the existing models provide only result like placed or not, without giving an explanation. To address this gap ,this paper introduce an explainable AI-based system which predict the placement readiness score along with the impact of every factor on performance, and also give the actions for improvement. It also provides the student with a list of companies that he or she would be eligible for.

This system uses different machine learning algorithms, to find a best fit model for predicting the placement. Student-related technical attributes and non-technical attributes are used as input features. The best performing model Random forest is selected of accuracy score 89.5 % .To increase the transparency, the system combines the shape, explainable AI technique to analyse the contribution of each feature.

Keywords:-*Campus placement prediction, Explainable AI, SHAP, Predictive analysis.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Campus placement plays a very important role in the career of the students and also improve the academic reputation of the educational institutions. In today's competitive job market, students are viewed not just by their entire academic achievement, but also by their technical skills, the ability to solve problems, their internship, and their projects that they have completed during their studies, as well as their soft skills. As a result, the traditional methods of placement are mostly centered around academic scores and manual checks. Due to this, they often do not see their actual potential in a student, or provide specific advice to them. [1]

Campus placements have become the key to one's career now. Educational institutions need to do a better job of placing students for better use of resources and personal support. This helps to match the students to the right jobs depending upon the skills they possess. While academic scores were used in the past, it did not take into consideration important factors such as family background and personal interests. Now, Machine Learning (ML) helps institutions to understand these complex factors better. Earlier, ML was only used to predict whether a student will pass or drop out. Today, it can predict certain job placements based on many different details of a student. However, current research often focuses on just one method, or does not take into account things such as socio-economic status and advanced data cleaning. This study aims to address these gaps by applying several ML models and improved data techniques to make more precise placement predictions. [2]

Placement records are the prime measure of a college's success and lures new students. For this reason, colleges need a system to analyze and predict placement results. Our system use classification algorithms such as Decision Tree, Linear

Regression, Multiple Linear Regression and Random Forest Algorithm to predict whether an undergraduate student will get a job or not. By analyzing academic information (such as total marks, backlogs and credits from previous years) the model predicts the likelihood of a student being recruited. This helps both the students and the institutions improve their results. The primary goal of this system is the prediction of whether a student will be placed in the process of recruitment on campus or not. These algorithms are trained based on the data of previous years students to find patterns and accurately predict placements. [3]

This is the overall analysis of this topic. In addition to general placement prediction, the proposed system extends its functionality to explain what students need to improve, eligibility analysis specific to a company where the predictions are aligned with realistic dashboard-style visualization with probability gauges and graphical analysis, which is also included to increase interpretability and usability.

The main goals of this research are:

1. To compare several machine learning models and choose the most accurate algorithm for placing the prediction.
2. To predict individual student placement probability accurately enough to be regarded as reliable.
3. To offer explainable insights in feature contributions using SHAP.
4. To assess eligibility of companies according to student performance.
5. To provide results in an intuitive and professional way with the help of visualizations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Campus placement prediction has been extensively investigated as an application in the field of data analysis and machine learning in education. Early studies were mostly done on the understanding of the

trends of placement based on historical institutional data. Studies like [4] and [5] used placement records that were gathered over several academic years to determine key patterns that determine placement performance. These works emphasized the data preprocessing, statistical analysis and visualization techniques to understand the institutional placement outcomes. Although these studies contributed very useful information about trends of placement, they were mostly descriptive research and did not address predictive modeling at their individual student level.

A detailed analytical approach to campus placement data was shown in [6]. In this work, the authors used several machine learning classifiers namely Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, to interpret the results of placement. The study showed that the supervised learning techniques are able to capture the relationships between academic attributes and placement status effectively. However, the focus of this research was more on institutional analysis and historical validation and did not put much emphasis on real-time predictions or system deployment.

Several studies focused on the prediction of placement outcome supervised machine learning techniques applied to student academic performances. Various researches like [7] and [8] were done using student-level academic and skill-based attributes to predict the placement status. These studies indicated that successful use of machine learning classifiers can predict if a student is likely to be placed. However, much of these systems were tested only in experimental settings and lacked a comprehensive end-to-end implementation that could be used in an institutional environment.

Comparative studies on the performance of several machine learning algorithms have also been reported in the literature. In [1] and [9], different classification models were compared in order to determine the

best predictor. These studies underlined a general observation that tree-based methods and ensemble methods perform generally better than traditional classifiers. Despite the positive outcome the main focus was still on algorithm comparison rather than practical usability or deployment.

Ensemble based prediction techniques were discussed more in [10]. The authors proposed a voting based ensemble model by combining multiple classifiers in order to improve the accuracy and robustness of prediction. The ensemble approach outperformed the individual models demonstrating the effectiveness of the combination of multiple learning techniques. However, the performance improvement was mainly focused in this study and there was no focus on interpretability and result explanation.

Explainability in educational Prediction systems has attracted attention over the past years. The study [11] targeted on creating interpretable machine learning models for identifying students at academic risk. Although this research was aimed at academic performance and not at placement in campus courses, it did point to the importance of transparent and explainable prediction models. Such explainability is very relevant for placement prediction systems, in which stakeholders want to know the results of predictions, to make informed decisions.

The role of exploratory data analysis in placement prediction was described in [12]. This study showed that detailed analysis of the feature distributions and their relationships can be very much helpful check the prediction reliability. The authors emphasized that it is essential to understand the data before the development of the model to build robust predictive systems. However, the study was relatively analytical and failed to incorporate the prediction model within a complete application framework.

3. METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

The data that is used for this research is structured in the form of structured datasets that are stored in CSV files. Each record in the dataset represents an individual student and includes attributes related to academic performance, technical skills, internships, certifications and training exposure. The dataset contains around 1000 records of students, which is enough for training a reliable machine learning model. The placement status of each student is included as the target variable indicating whether the student is placed or not placed. Since the output variable is already labeled, the dataset can be used for supervised machine learning. Additionally, another data set that includes company-wise placement results and

eligibility criteria is used to analyze placement results in different companies.

Data Preprocessing

Before using machine learning methods, the data collected is processed for garbage values so that its quality and consistency are improved. Duplicate entries, if any, are identified and removed, in order to avoid biased learning. Missing or incomplete values are explored and treated accordingly in order to ensure reliability of the data sets. Categorical attributes are converted to numerical values so that they can be processed by machine learning algorithms. The dataset is then split with the input features and the target variable. These preprocessing steps help in reducing noise, improving data consistency, and making the dataset suitable for model training.

Fig.1

Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory Data Analysis is carried out to know the underlying structure and behavior of the dataset. Statistical summaries and visual analysis techniques are used to study academic scores, skill levels and placement outcomes. It is useful in finding patterns and relations between student attributes and placement results. It also helps in identifying class imbalance

and outliers which may adversely affect the prediction performance. Insights gained from this stage help in the further feature selection and model development.

Feature Selection

Feature selection is performed in order to determine the most relevant attributes that have a significant effect on the prediction of the placement. Since not all features

contribute equally to final outcome, the features that have low relevance and high redundancy are removed from the final feature set. Selecting meaningful features only will reduce computational complexity and reduce the risk of overfitting. This step is to ensure that the prediction model focuses on important academic and skill-related factors that have a direct impact on placement outcomes.

ML Model Selection

Multiple supervised machine learning algorithms are considered for finding the best possible model for campus placement prediction. Algorithms such as Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest and other classifiers are tested on their capacity to deal with structured educational data. The final model selection is based on the performance metrics, stability of the prediction and the generalization capability. The model selected offers a trade-off between the accuracy and the interpretability of the model, which will be useful for real-world deployment in an academic environment.

Model Deployment

The task of predicting placement on campus is stated as a binary classification problem, in which the aim is to determine whether a student will be placed or not placed. The preprocessed data set is split into training and testing set to ensure unbiased evaluation. During the training phase, the model learns from the correlation between the attributes of the students and the placement outcomes by updating the internal parameters. Feature scaling and normalization are performed using a trained preprocessing pipeline in order to achieve consistency between the training and prediction stages.

Model Evaluation

After the model has been trained, it is then evaluated on unseen test data in order to determine how well it can predict

outcomes. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score are used to evaluate the effectiveness of the model in both the placed and the non-placed classes. These metrics give an overall picture of the strengths and limitations of the model. Model evaluation helps in verifying the reliability of the system and finding possible areas for further improvement.

Explainable AI (Xai)

To increase transparency and trust in the prediction process, explainable artificial intelligence techniques are made a part of the system. XAI methods are applied to interpret the effects of various input features on the prediction outcome of the model. This step lets the academic stakeholders understand the rationale for placement predictions instead of just looking at numerical outputs. Explainability ensures that the decisions that the model makes are understandable, fair and in line with academic expectations.

System Implementation

The trained and evaluated machine learning model is interfaced in a Python-based application with a web interface. The system lets the user enter the details of the students, which are fed through the trained prediction pipeline to generate the placement predictions. The system also checks the eligibility of students based on company-specific criteria and displays the company-wise probabilities for placement. This implementation turns the model into a decision-support tool for the placement cells and academic administrators.

Result Interpretation

The final output of the system consists of placement probability, predicted placement status and company wise eligibility analysis. Visual representation in the form of charts and tables are used to communicate the results clearly to the

users. Result interpretation assists stakeholders in making informed decisions about student training and placement preparation and career guidance using data-driven insights.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Tools and Technologies

The system is powered by Anaconda An open-source distribution of Python and R Programming languages designed for data science, machine learning, and AI as an environment management and package distribution platform. Jupyter notebook is an open source, web-based interactive computing environment to be used for exploratory analysis, experimentation and validation of result before deployment. The reason behind conducting the system is the use of pythonversion 3.13 because of its stability and wide support. Libraries used for experimentations are Numpy for number crunching, Pandas for data handling, Scikit-learn for a fundamental machine learning framework, SHAP for explainable AI,Streamlit for web-based user interface ,Matplotlib for visualization , and Joblib for saving a model.

Dataset Description

The system uses a dataset which is consisting of 1000 rows and 13 columns where 12 are the input feature and one is

the target variable. Each record for the dataset that is used for the system represents a different student and contains a mix of academic performance attributes, technical skill evaluations, experiential learning factors, and soft skills attributes. Academic features indicate a consistency and performance over the semesters and technical attributes include a proficiency in core subjects; programming skills and problem solving ability. Some experiential features such as internships, project work and certifications are included to capture practical exposure outside of a classroom. In addition, soft skill indicators are taken into consideration of communication and professional readiness, which are more and more an issue in placement evaluations.

The target variable in the dataset shows the placement outcome of the student, which is represented as a binary label whether the student was placed or not placed. This formulation enables the problem to be represented as a supervised classification problem.

Before experimentation, the data set was checked for completeness and consistency. Records with missing or ambiguous values were handled appropriately so as not to bias the learning of the model. Some of the rows in the dataset are provided below:

Current_CGPA	12th_Grade_Percent	10th_Grade_Percent	Coding_Problems	Events_Participated	Events_Ranks_Achieved	Avg_Sleep_Hours	Projects_Completed	Patents_Filed	Internships_Done	Soft_Skill_Score	No_of_Backlogs	Target: Placed
6.87	60	70	0	0	1	8.93	2	0	2	4	2	0
9.75	83.53	75.65	292	19	4	4.48	5	0	1	9	0	1
8.66	91.64	94.45	208	10	0	5.43	3	0	0	9	6	0
7.99	72.43	71.7	32	6	0	8.35	4	0	1	6	2	0
5.78	77.22	70	129	8	0	4.36	0	0	0	7	4	0
5.78	66.56	79.62	160	9	3	8.38	2	0	0	4	7	0
5.29	62.3	70	87	0	3	6.62	0	0	1	6	6	0
9.33	91.34	84.91	234	11	6	6.04	2	1	0	8	0	1
8.01	60	70	259	3	1	5.55	0	1	0	7	1	0
8.54	74.32	77.31	295	7	0	5.49	3	0	0	5	0	0
5.1	60	70	85	0	0	5.53	0	0	0	4	6	0
9.85	91.99	70	210	11	2	8.42	5	2	2	7	0	1
9.86	85.96	89.3	285	10	2	7.62	4	1	0	6	2	1
6.06	60	70	222	5	2	7.35	0	0	0	7	2	0
5.91	64.62	71.57	35	3	1	7.99	0	0	1	4	2	0
5.92	84.26	75.94	305	0	0	5.29	0	0	1	3	4	0
6.52	60	70	73	0	0	7.09	3	0	0	4	2	0
7.62	62.3	90.4	184	4	0	6.3	2	0	0	4	1	1
7.16	76.84	70	90	4	1	7.91	1	0	0	8	4	0
6.46	60	79.68	145	8	1	5.55	3	0	0	4	6	0
8.06	77.41	92.85	28	2	2	7.22	1	0	0	7	2	0
5.7	60	70.31	30	0	0	8.41	0	0	0	6	4	0
6.46	80.08	91.84	13	7	1	6.01	0	0	1	4	4	0
6.83	85.51	70	155	3	1	4.33	1	0	1	6	4	0

Data Pre-processing and Splitting

In the system ,the data set is cleaned and the categorical data is transferred to the numerical form . To test the generalization

of the model, the processed dataset was split into a training and testing dataset in an 80:20 split . The training data was used for the model learning , and the testing

data set was not seen during model training and was used only for performance evaluation. This strategy ensures that an unbiased evaluation is made and it avoids information leakage between the training and evaluation phases.

Model Training and Evaluation

In order to increase the accuracy of the model, multiple machine learning algorithms are trained on the same dataset. The algorithms applied include Random forest, Gradient Boosting, SVM, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN etc.

The trained models were compared based on their performance as per the selected evaluation metrics. The selection of the final model was not only based on the highest accuracy, but a consistent and stable performance in all the metrics. This selection method improve accuracy of the model.

Explainability with Gap Analysis and Eligibility Evaluation

The model applies Shap, an explainable AI technique during the evaluation phase. Feature contribution values were analysed in order to identify factors that have a positive or negative impact on placement outcomes. Negative feature contributions were linked to a specific skill gap to give meaningful insights on improvement. Additionally, predefined company-specific eligibility criteria were implemented to predicted student profiles to simulate real-life scenarios in the recruitment environment on campus and to test practical applicability.

5. RESULT ANALYSIS

Model Performance Evaluation

The dataset used for this study has multiple academic and skill-based attributes such as CGPA, academic percentages, number of coding problems, internships, projects, soft skills and backlogs. After the preprocessing and

feature scaling, the dataset was split into training and testing datasets with an 80:20 ratio..

Several supervised machine learning models were trained and tested, these included:

- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- Logistic Regression
- K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)
- Decision Tree
- Random Forest
- Gradient Boosting

The performance of each model was measured with the classification accuracy. Experimental results show that ensemble based models, especially Random Forest & Gradient Boosting models, performed better than traditional classifiers owing to their capability in capturing the nonlinear relationship and mitigating overfitting.

6. CONFUSION MATRIX ANALYSIS

The confusion matrix of the selected best model shows a high number of correctly classified instances for both placed and non-placed categories. The low false-positive and false-negative rates indicate that the model reliably distinguishes between employable and non-employable students. This validates the robustness of the proposed framework.

7. EXPLAINABLE AI (SHAP) ANALYSIS

In order to overcome the black-box nature of machine learning models, SHAP analysis was used to explain individual predictions. The SHAP bar plot is used to

highlight the contribution of each feature towards the final decision. Also, it show graph like below:

No	Feature	SHAP Impact	Analysis
1	Current_CGPA	0.209172	Strong Point
2	No_of_Backlogs	0.137753	Strong Point
3	Internships_Done	0.103135	Strong Point
4	CodingProblemSolved	0.032719	Strong Point
5	Events_Participated	0.021099	Strong Point
6	Projects_Completed	0.019395	Strong Point
7	Avg_Sleep_Hours	0.016853	Strong Point
8	10thGrade_Percentage	0.005591	Strong Point
9	EventsRanksAchieved	0.000616	Strong Point
10	Patents_Filed	-0.00252	Needs Improvement
11	12thGrade_Percentage	-0.01146	Needs Improvement

Results reveal that:

- CGPA, coding problem solved, internship and soft skills have positive impacts on the probability of placement.
- Backlogs and less project adversely affect the employability.

This is consistent with the results of more recent research on the importance of skills in the workplace and the increasing importance of practical skills and internships in addition to academics.

Company Specific Placement Prediction

The model further checks the eligibility of the students against predefined company criteria such as minimum CGPA and

maximum allowed backlogs. Companies like TCS, Infosys, Amazon, Microsoft and Google were taken into consideration.

Results categorize eligibility into:

- Eligible & String Chance
- Eligible & Moderate Chance
- Eligible but low chance
- Not eligible

The feature is especially good for students to strategically target companies and prepare accordingly. Prior studies also suggest company-specific customization as an enhancement for future work, which is successfully adopted in this work.

No	Company	Eligibility	Placement Probability (%)	Status
1	TCS	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
2	Infosys	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
3	Wipro	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
4	Accenture	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
5	Cognizant	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
6	Capgemini	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
7	HCL Technologies	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
8	IBM	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong

				Chance
9	Amazon	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
10	Microsoft	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance
11	Google	Yes	96.0	Eligible and Strong Chance

The above graph indicates what the feature impact is and what the action plan is.

8. CONCLUSION

The struggle that is faced by students in comprehending their level of preparation especially their strength and weaknesses is minimized through this study. This study presents explainable AI based machine learning campus placement prediction system. It includes streamlit UI to take inputs from students and predict the placement score along with importance of each factor. In addition, it creates a list of eligible companies for each student. The

model is trained on a dataset of more than 1000 records and several machine learning algorithms are tried, one of which the Random Forest model has the highest accuracy. This strategy successfully addresses the current gap by providing transparent, individualized and interpretable feedback, empowering students to work on specific improvements and be more strategic about their campus placements.

REFERENCES

1. Senthilkumar, K. R., Vijayarajkumar, P. T., Sivasankari, & Balamani. (2023). Campus placement prediction using machine learning techniques. *Handbook of Research in Big Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*.
2. Ruparel, M., & Swaminarayan, P. (2025). Enhanced student placement prediction using machine learning: A comparative evaluation of algorithms. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*.
3. Bhagat, S., Dhavale, S., Hegde, N., Jadhav, G., & Patil, P. (2024). Campus

- placement prediction using machine learning. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*.
4. Clemente, C. J., & Kwak, M. (2022). Utilizing data science and analytics in predicting campus placement. *Issues in Information Systems*.
 5. Rao, A. V. S. S., Sreeram, K. N., Sahithi, D. J. S. L., Abhinav, K., Rayudu, R. S., & Dyuthi, M. L. (2025). Campus placement prediction using machine learning. *Journal of Computer Science*.
 6. Indoori, A., Patwari, S., & Prathima, T. (n.d.). Analysis of campus placement data: A case study. *Grenze International Journal of Engineering and Technology*.
 7. Khandale, S., & Bhoite, S. (2019). Campus placement analyzer: Using supervised machine learning algorithms. *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*.
 8. Shahane, P. (2022). Campus placements prediction & analysis using machine learning. In *Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on Emerging Smart Computing and Informatics (ESCI)*. AISSMS Institute of Information Technology, Pune, India.
 9. Maurya, L. S., Hussain, M. S., & Singh, S. (2021). Developing classifiers through machine learning algorithms for student placement prediction based on academic performance. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 35(6), 403–420.
 10. Dutta, S., & Bandyopadhyay, S. K. (2020). Forecasting of campus placement for students using ensemble voting classifier. *Asian Journal of Research in Computer Science*.
 11. Alwarthan, S., Aslam, N., & Khan, I. U. (2022). An explainable model for identifying at-risk students at higher education. *IEEE Access*.
 12. Nagaria, J., & Velan, S. (n.d.). Utilizing exploratory data analysis for the prediction of campus placement for educational institutions.